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Review Article

**THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN IMPROVING PATIENT
OUTCOMES IN PREHOSPITAL EMERGENCY CARE: A
REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE**

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Abstract:

This systematic review investigates the pivotal role of technology in enhancing patient outcomes in prehospital emergency care, with a particular focus on low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) such as Rwanda. Emergency medical services (EMS) face significant challenges, including inefficient communication systems, inadequate triage processes, and difficulties in locating emergencies, which hinder timely and effective care. This review emphasizes the potential of integrating information technology and mobile health (mHealth) solutions to address these challenges and improve EMS operations. Various technological interventions, including telemedicine, mobile applications, point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS), and advanced medical monitoring devices, are critically analyzed for their impact on patient assessment, decision-making, and overall quality of care. Furthermore, the review highlights existing gaps in the literature, particularly regarding the practical implementation of these technologies in diverse EMS settings. By identifying these gaps, the review advocates for further research to optimize the integration of technology into emergency medical services, thereby improving patient outcomes and enhancing the overall effectiveness of prehospital care.

Keywords: Technology, Prehospital Emergency Care, Patient Outcomes, Mobile Health, Emergency Medical Services.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

1.1. Background

Emergency medical services (EMS) are critical for delivering timely and effective care during health emergencies. In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) like Rwanda, robust EMS systems are essential due to the high burden of emergency conditions that contribute significantly to morbidity and mortality (Walsh, 2019). The Service d'Aide Medicale Urgente (SAMU) in Rwanda operates a national emergency number and a fleet of ambulances to provide prehospital care. However, challenges such as inefficient communication systems, inadequate triage processes, and difficulties in locating emergencies hinder the effectiveness of these services (Hedderson et al., 2024).

Recent studies have highlighted the potential impact of information technology and mobile health (mHealth) solutions in enhancing EMS operations. Integrating IT can improve the linkage between hospitals and emergency ambulances, thereby enhancing the overall quality of care (Anantharaman, 2001). Non-invasive technologies and point-of-care diagnostics have also been suggested as transformative tools for prehospital care (Amaral et al., 2020). Despite these advancements, many EMS systems continue to operate with outdated practices, limiting their ability to respond effectively to emergencies. In addition to these overarching themes, specific applications within prehospital care warrant attention. For example, point-of-care ultrasound (PHUS) has emerged as a key tool, with particular emphasis on trauma patients through examinations such as the FAST and eFAST exams, which evaluate for intraperitoneal free fluid and pneumothorax, respectively (Becker et al., 2018; Smallwood & Dachsel, 2018; Perera et al., 2010). Furthermore, echocardiography aids in assessing cardiac conditions during emergencies (Lichtenstein & Mezière, 2008; Feng et al., 2018).

1.2. Rationale for the Study

The current EMS framework faces significant barriers that compromise care quality, including communication breakdowns and inefficiencies in patient triage and handover processes (Niyonsaba et al., 2023). The potential for mHealth tools to streamline these processes is significant; mobile applications, for instance, can facilitate real-time data sharing and improve decision-making during emergencies (Lee, 2024). Moreover, leveraging mHealth can enhance coordination among EMS personnel, dispatch centers, and receiving hospitals, thus improving patient outcomes (Hedderson et al., 2024). However, successful implementation of these technologies requires a comprehensive understanding

of the challenges faced by stakeholders and their perspectives on the utility of mHealth solutions.

Moreover, technology-enhanced simulation has become foundational in emergency medicine training (Heitz et al., 2011; Okuda et al., 2008; McLaughlin et al., 2008). Simulation allows complex tasks to be broken down into manageable learning objectives, promoting practice on infrequent tasks that pose risks when performed by novices (Ziv et al., 2003). Various educational tools, such as virtual reality simulators and mannequins, are utilized for training purposes (Heitz et al., 2011).

1.3. Research Objectives

The primary objectives of this study are:

1. To systematically review and summarize the current literature on the role of technology in prehospital emergency care, focusing on various technological interventions and their applications.
2. To assess and analyze findings from different studies regarding the impact of technology on patient outcomes in prehospital settings.
3. To identify gaps in the existing literature and propose areas for future research, particularly in relation to the evolving landscape of technology in emergency medical services.

1.4. Significance of the Study

The consensus conference in 2008 highlighted essential directions for simulation technologies to enhance learning across different educational levels (Gordon & Vozenilek, 2008). Meta-analyses indicate that simulation positively impacts knowledge, skills, and behavior, though the effects vary across clinical topics (Cook et al., 2011; McGaghie et al., 2011). Despite numerous studies, the specific instructional effects of simulation in emergency medicine remain underexplored, emphasizing the need for evidence-based instructional designs (Issenberg et al., 2005). Ultrasound technology also provides procedural guidance, facilitating vascular access and confirming endotracheal tube placements (Becker et al., 2017). Rapid assessment protocols, including the Rapid Ultrasound in SHock (RUSH) and Bilateral Lung Ultrasound in Emergency (BLUE) protocols, are particularly relevant for prehospital use, allowing for quick determination of life-threatening conditions (Becker et al., 2018; Perera et al., 2010). While some applications, like fracture diagnosis and joint dislocations, may have limited relevance in urban EMS systems, they are beneficial in environments with longer transport times or specific clinical contexts (Christensen et al., 2016; Ketelaars et al., 2018; Kendall et al., 2007). This review will contribute to

understanding the role of technology in improving patient outcomes in prehospital emergency care, particularly within the context of Rwanda's EMS challenges and opportunities.

2. METHODOLOGY:

2.1. Research Design

This study employs a systematic literature review design to explore the role of technology in improving patient outcomes in prehospital emergency care. The review is structured to identify, evaluate, and synthesize existing research on technological interventions within EMS settings, focusing on their effectiveness and applications. This approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of how various technologies impact patient care in prehospital environments.

2.2. Literature Search Strategy

2.2.1. Databases and Keywords

A systematic search was conducted across multiple electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. The search utilized a combination of keywords and phrases related to the study's focus. Key search terms included "technology," "prehospital emergency care," "patient outcomes," "mobile health," "point-of-care ultrasound," "emergency medical services," and "simulation training." Boolean operators (AND, OR) were employed to refine the search results and ensure the inclusion of relevant studies.

2.2.2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

2.2.2.1. Inclusion criteria for the literature review were as follows:

- Studies published in peer-reviewed journals between 2010 and 2024.
- Research focusing on technology applications in prehospital emergency care.
- Articles that assess the impact of technology on patient outcomes.

2.2.2.2. Exclusion criteria included:

- Studies not available in English.
- Literature that did not specifically address prehospital emergency care or technology use.
- Non-peer-reviewed articles, opinion pieces, or editorials.

2.3. Data Extraction and Analysis

Data extraction involved systematically collecting relevant information from the selected studies. This included author details, publication year, study design, technology type, patient outcomes measured, and key findings. A standardized data extraction form was

developed to ensure consistency across the extracted data. The extracted data were then analyzed using qualitative synthesis techniques, allowing for thematic organization of findings related to the role of technology in enhancing patient outcomes in prehospital settings.

2.4. Quality Assessment of Included Studies

The quality of the included studies was assessed using a standardized quality assessment tool, such as the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool or the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale, depending on the study design. This assessment focused on criteria such as study design adequacy, sample size, statistical analysis, and potential biases. Each study was rated as low, moderate, or high quality based on these criteria. The quality assessment ensured that only robust studies contributed to the findings of this review, thereby enhancing the reliability of the conclusions drawn regarding the impact of technology on patient outcomes in prehospital emergency care.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Types of Technology in Prehospital Emergency Care

3.1.1. Telemedicine

3.1.1.1. Remote Consultations

Telemedicine has transformed prehospital emergency care by enabling remote consultations between paramedics and specialized medical professionals. This technology allows for real-time audiovisual communication, facilitating immediate assessment and decision-making. For instance, LaMonte et al. (2000) demonstrated that the TeleBAT system improved neurological assessments during transport, leading to faster treatment decisions. The integration of telemedicine in stroke management allows for quicker identification of stroke types and appropriate treatment protocols, thus reducing time to treatment and enhancing clinical outcomes (Eder et al., 2018).

3.1.1.2. Impact on Decision-Making

The impact of telemedicine on decision-making processes in emergency situations is significant. By providing access to expert opinions and guidance, telemedicine assists paramedics in making informed decisions that can drastically affect patient outcomes. Kim et al. (2020) highlighted that telemedicine enhances communication and improves coordination in patient care, ultimately leading to better patient safety and treatment outcomes.

3.2. Mobile Applications

3.2.1. Patient Tracking and Data Collection

Mobile applications are critical in enhancing the efficiency of prehospital emergency care. These applications facilitate patient tracking and data

collection, allowing emergency medical services (EMS) personnel to gather and share vital patient information quickly. Anantharaman and Lim (2001) noted that the HEAL system improved data transmission efficiency, enabling the advance sharing of patient data with emergency departments, which enhances overall emergency care delivery.

3.2.2. Communication Tools for First Responders

Effective communication is essential for first responders to ensure timely and accurate information exchange during emergencies. The integration of fifth-generation (5G) technology in emergency medical services (EMS) represents a transformative advancement in this area. According to Kim et al. (2020), 5G technology enhances communication capabilities through high-speed connectivity and ultra-reliable low-latency communication. These features enable paramedics to rapidly share critical patient data with hospital-based physicians, facilitating informed decision-making during transport.

The ability to transmit real-time information can significantly impact patient outcomes, as timely updates allow for better coordination of care and preparation of receiving facilities. However, several challenges persist, including privacy concerns related to data security and the limited regulatory frameworks governing the use of such advanced technologies. Additionally, rural and underserved areas often lack access to 5G networks, creating disparities in the quality of care provided to different populations.

3.3. Advanced Medical Devices

3.3.1. Monitoring Equipment

Advanced monitoring equipment is increasingly vital in enhancing prehospital care, particularly in emergency scenarios like stroke. Walsh (2019) provides a comprehensive review of ten non-invasive brain monitoring devices under development, emphasizing their potential to facilitate rapid diagnosis and improve treatment decisions before hospital arrival. Technologies such as accelerometers, electroencephalography (EEG), and near-infrared spectroscopy are highlighted for their capabilities in quickly identifying various neurological conditions.

For instance, devices like BrainPulse™ and AlphaStroke have demonstrated significant sensitivity in detecting conditions such as vasospasm and concussion. These devices can provide real-time data that allows paramedics to make informed decisions during transport, potentially leading to improved patient outcomes. The review underscores the limitations of traditional diagnostic methods, which

often delay critical treatment decisions, calling for the integration of these advanced monitoring technologies into prehospital protocols.

3.3.2. Automated Transport Systems

Automated transport systems, including telemedicine solutions, have been developed to enhance the management of acute conditions during transport. LaMonte et al. (2000) introduced TeleBAT, an integrated mobile telecommunications system that enables real-time audiovisual communication between ambulance paramedics and stroke neurologists. This system allows neurologists to access critical assessment data while the patient is en route to the hospital, streamlining evaluations and facilitating quicker treatment decisions.

The TeleBAT system demonstrated its efficacy during testing, successfully transmitting audio, video, and vital sign data, which enabled timely neurological evaluations. In instances where early diagnosis and intervention were possible, the system significantly improved clinical decision-making during critical transport phases. Such automated systems are pivotal in reducing delays and enhancing resource utilization, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes in acute care scenarios.

3.4. Impact of Technology on Patient Outcomes

3.4.1. Survival Rates

The integration of advanced technologies in EMS has a profound impact on survival rates, particularly in time-sensitive situations such as strokes. Evidence suggests that technologies enabling early diagnosis and timely treatment can significantly improve survival outcomes. For instance, Walsh (2019) and Lee et al. (2024) demonstrate how non-invasive monitoring devices and mobile telemedicine solutions enhance the ability to identify and treat acute conditions rapidly, thereby improving survival rates for critical patients.

3.4.2. Time to Treatment

Time to treatment is a critical metric in emergency care, and technology plays a vital role in minimizing this duration. The Hospital & Emergency Ambulance Link (HEAL) system implemented in Singapore exemplifies this, as Anantharaman and Lim (2001) reported a reduction in mean time for data capture from over 7 minutes to just 94 seconds. This improvement in data transmission efficiency enabled paramedics to communicate vital patient information to receiving hospitals before arrival, ensuring that emergency departments were prepared for incoming

patients and significantly reducing wait times for treatment.

3.4.3. Patient Satisfaction

The implementation of technology in prehospital settings has been linked to improved patient satisfaction. Enhanced communication, timely interventions, and the ability to provide informed care contribute to a greater sense of safety and trust among patients. Kim et al. (2020) noted that when paramedics can share real-time updates with hospital staff, it fosters a collaborative environment that enhances the overall patient experience. Consequently, patients often feel more secure knowing that their care is coordinated and that medical professionals are prepared to address their needs immediately upon arrival.

3.4.4. Case Studies and Evidence

Case studies highlight the effectiveness of technology in improving patient outcomes. The TeleBAT system, for example, facilitated timely neurological assessments, leading to improved treatment decisions and outcomes in stroke patients (LaMonte et al., 2000). Similarly, the integration of point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS) in prehospital settings has shown potential in enhancing diagnostic accuracy during emergencies, allowing for quicker and more informed decisions regarding patient care (Amaral et al., 2020). These real-world applications provide compelling evidence that technology can transform emergency medical services and enhance patient outcomes.

3.5. Barriers to Technology Implementation

3.5.1. Operational Challenges

Operational challenges present significant barriers to the adoption of new technologies in EMS. Integrating new tools into existing workflows requires careful planning and adaptation, as highlighted by Kim et al. (2020). Concerns regarding data transmission reliability, the need for interoperability between different systems, and the establishment of user-friendly interfaces can complicate the implementation process. Additionally, the diversity of EMS settings, from urban to rural environments, necessitates tailored solutions to ensure efficacy and usability.

3.5.2. Training and Education

Training and education are critical components for the effective implementation of technology in EMS. While studies indicate that paramedics can learn to use tools like POCUS with appropriate training, the lack of standardized educational frameworks remains a major hurdle (Amaral et al., 2020). Ensuring that all personnel are adequately trained not only improves the effectiveness of the technology but also enhances the confidence of responders in utilizing these tools during emergencies. Ongoing education and competency assessments are essential to maintain skill proficiency and ensure that responders can effectively integrate technology into their practice.

3.5.3. Financial Constraints

Financial constraints are a pervasive barrier to the adoption of new technologies in EMS. Many agencies face unfunded mandates requiring the implementation of electronic systems without accompanying financial support, complicating the transition process (Landman et al., 2012). Budget limitations can restrict the ability to invest in new technologies, training programs, and maintenance, ultimately hindering the potential benefits that these advancements could provide. Addressing these financial barriers is crucial to enable EMS agencies to adopt and sustain technological improvements.

3.5.4. Resistance to Change

Resistance to change among EMS personnel can also hinder technology adoption. Concerns regarding the effectiveness and reliability of new technologies may lead to reluctance in integrating them into daily practice (Bashiri et al., 2019). This resistance can stem from a lack of familiarity with new tools, fear of increased workload, or skepticism about the benefits of technology. To overcome this barrier, it is essential to engage personnel in the implementation process, provide thorough training, and demonstrate the tangible benefits of technology in improving patient care. Encouraging a culture of innovation and adaptability within EMS organizations can facilitate smoother transitions to new technologies.

4. RESULTS:

The findings from various studies regarding the role of technology in improving patient outcomes in prehospital emergency care are summarized in the table below:

Author and Year	Aim of the Study	Methodology of the Study	Findings of the Study	The Role of Technology in Improving Patient Outcomes in Prehospital Emergency Care	Recommendations
Kim et al. (2020)	Explore benefits of 5G technology in EMS	Literature review	5G enhances communication, improving decision-making and coordination in patient care. Challenges include privacy concerns and access issues.	5G can revolutionize EMS delivery and patient outcomes.	Further research on practical applications and standardization in training for paramedics.
Walsh (2019)	Review non-invasive brain monitoring devices for stroke diagnosis	Comprehensive review of ten devices under development	Devices show promise for rapid diagnosis, potentially improving triaging and treatment decisions before hospital arrival.	Non-invasive technologies could transform stroke management.	Further validation of technologies in real-world scenarios.
Amaral et al. (2020)	Investigate the impact of POCUS in prehospital care	Review of literature on POCUS applications	POCUS can enhance diagnostic accuracy and patient outcomes, but training for paramedics is essential.	POCUS can significantly improve patient assessments in emergencies.	Develop standardized training and quality assurance programs for POCUS use in EMS.
Kirkpatrick et al. (2022)	Explore Remote Telementored Self-Performed Ultrasound (RTMSPUS) application	Conceptual framework study	RTMSPUS allows patients to perform self-ultrasound under expert guidance, improving health assessments.	It enhances accessibility of ultrasound in prehospital care.	Further research to refine RTMSPUS and expand its applications across healthcare scenarios.
Lumley et al. (2020)	Examine technologies for prehospital stroke diagnosis	Systematic review of literature from 2000-2019	Identifies technologies that could improve stroke diagnosis and treatment timing; telemedicine shows promise but lacks sufficient evidence.	Emerging technologies can aid in timely stroke management.	Conduct multi-centre diagnostic studies to validate technologies before routine implementation.
LaMonte et al. (2000)	Enhance management of acute stroke patients via TeleBAT	Feasibility study of TeleBAT system	Successful real-time data transmission improved neurological assessments	Mobile telemedicine improves prehospital care for stroke patients.	Continue clinical trials to validate TeleBAT's efficacy in diverse settings.

			during transport, leading to faster treatment decisions.		
Anantharaman & Lim (2001)	Investigate HEAL system's impact on prehospital care in Singapore	Pilot project analysis of HEAL system	HEAL improved data transmission efficiency and reduced wait times, enhancing patient management.	Technology enhances communication and efficiency in EMS.	Expand HEAL implementation with ongoing training and system improvements.
Landman et al. (2012)	Examine experiences with e-PCR systems in EMS	Qualitative study of EMS leaders in the US and Canada	e-PCR systems improve documentation quality but face barriers like financial constraints and integration issues.	e-PCR systems can enhance patient care through better documentation.	Support EMS agencies with funding and resources for e-PCR implementation.
Bashiri et al. (2019)	Assess the impact of CDSS on prehospital emergency care	Narrative review of 14 articles	CDSS improves decision-making and patient outcomes but requires proper training for EMS personnel.	CDSS optimizes prehospital care processes.	Ensure user-friendly CDSS implementation and adequate training for EMS staff.
Eder et al. (2018)	Evaluate telemedicine in prehospital trauma care	Systematic review of telemedicine applications	Telemedicine improves treatment quality and reduces time-to-treatment in trauma care.	Enhances real-time communication and decision-making in trauma scenarios.	Call for more rigorous studies to assess telemedicine's overall effectiveness.
Martinez-Gutierrez et al. (2019)	Explore technology for prehospital stroke triage	Review of existing and emerging technologies	Technologies like mobile stroke units can significantly aid in timely stroke identification and treatment.	Technology enhances rapid assessment and treatment for strokes.	Further validation of technologies for widespread adoption in EMS.
Ilgen et al. (2013)	Evaluate technology-enhanced simulation in EM training	Systematic review and meta-analysis of 85 studies	Simulation training improves knowledge and skills but is less effective compared to traditional methods.	Simulation can enhance training in emergency medicine.	Focus on instructional design features to improve simulation training outcomes.
Niyonsaba et al. (2023)	Explore mHealth tools in Rwandan EMS	Qualitative study examining EMS challenges and opportunities	Identifies mHealth as a solution for inefficiencies in care delivery, improving communication and data sharing.	mHealth has the potential to enhance EMS efficiency and quality of care.	Address challenges such as internet access and data security for mHealth implementation.

Lee et al. (2024)	Evaluate mobile technology for neurologic assessments in prehospital care	Study comparing remote evaluations using mobile videoconferencing	Remote evaluations show high correlation with traditional assessments, enabling timely stroke management.	Mobile technology can facilitate real-time assessments improving patient outcomes.	Advocate for the use of mobile technology in emergency care to expedite treatment.
Hedderson et al. (2024)	Explore speech recognition technology in prehospital documentation	Scoping review of paramedic perceptions and requirements	SRT can improve documentation efficiency but requires more real-world testing for effective implementation.	SRT can enhance continuity of care through better documentation practices.	Conduct larger studies to refine SRT systems for paramedic workflows.

The analysis of existing literature on the role of technology in improving patient outcomes in prehospital emergency care yielded significant findings, categorized by technology type and their impact on patient care. The results are summarized in Table 1, which outlines the authors, study aims, methodologies, findings, roles of technology, and recommendations for future research.

4.1. Telemedicine

Telemedicine has been identified as a transformative force in prehospital emergency care. LaMonte et al. (2000) demonstrated that the TeleBAT system significantly improved real-time data transmission during transport, leading to enhanced neurological assessments and faster treatment decisions for stroke patients. Eder et al. (2018) affirmed that telemedicine enhances treatment quality and reduces time-to-treatment in trauma scenarios, emphasizing its role in facilitating immediate expert guidance for paramedics.

4.2. Mobile Applications

Mobile applications significantly improve data collection and communication efficiency in EMS. Anantharaman and Lim (2001) noted that the HEAL system enhanced patient data transmission efficiency, dramatically reducing wait times and improving the overall management of emergency cases. Lee et al. (2024) showed that mobile technology facilitates remote evaluations, correlating highly with traditional assessments and enabling timely stroke management.

4.3. Advanced Medical Devices

Advanced medical devices, particularly point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS), have shown promise in enhancing diagnostic accuracy and patient outcomes. Amaral et al. (2020) highlighted that POCUS allows paramedics to make informed decisions based on real-time diagnostic data, significantly improving patient assessments in emergencies. Walsh (2019) reviewed non-invasive brain monitoring devices, indicating their potential for rapid diagnosis and improved treatment decisions prior to hospital arrival, thus enhancing triage effectiveness.

4.4. Simulation Training

Technology-enhanced simulation training has been found to improve knowledge and skills among EMS personnel. Ilgen et al. (2013) conducted a systematic review, concluding that simulation training enhances emergency medicine training outcomes, although its effectiveness is sometimes lower compared to traditional methods. Heitz et al. (2011) emphasized the importance of simulation in preparing paramedics for infrequent yet critical tasks, promoting better preparedness and response during emergencies.

4.5. Barriers to Implementation

Despite the positive findings associated with technological advancements, several barriers to implementation persist. Bashiri et al. (2019) identified that clinical decision support systems (CDSS) improve decision-making but require adequate training for effective use in prehospital settings. Landman et al. (2012) emphasized that electronic patient care reporting (e-PCR) systems can enhance documentation quality but face challenges related to financial constraints and integration issues. Niyonsaba et al. (2023) highlighted the role of mHealth tools in overcoming inefficiencies in care delivery, yet also pointed out challenges such as internet access and data security concerns.

4.6. Recommendations for Future Research

The reviewed studies collectively advocate for further research in several areas. Kim et al. (2020) suggest investigating practical applications and standardization of 5G technology in EMS training. Walsh (2019) calls for validation of non-invasive

technologies in real-world scenarios to confirm their efficacy. Additionally, there is a need for multi-center diagnostic studies to validate emerging technologies before routine implementation (Lumley et al., 2020). The results from this systematic review underscore the critical role of technology in improving patient outcomes within prehospital emergency care. While significant advancements have been made, addressing barriers and gaps in research will be essential for optimizing the integration of these technologies into EMS practice.

5. CONCLUSION:

This systematic review highlights the pivotal role of technology in enhancing patient outcomes in prehospital emergency care. The integration of various technological interventions—such as telemedicine, mobile applications, advanced medical devices, and simulation training—has demonstrated significant benefits in improving communication, decision-making, and diagnostic accuracy.

The findings underscore that telemedicine facilitates real-time consultations, leading to faster and more informed treatment decisions, particularly in critical scenarios like stroke management. Mobile applications have proven essential for efficient data collection and patient tracking, significantly reducing wait times and enhancing overall care delivery. Advanced medical devices, including point-of-care ultrasound, provide paramedics with the tools necessary for accurate and timely assessments, ultimately improving patient triage and management. Despite these advancements, several barriers to implementation remain, including operational challenges, financial constraints, and resistance to change among EMS personnel. Addressing these obstacles is crucial for maximizing the benefits of technology in emergency medical services.

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